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A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF FDI IN RETAIL ON INDIAN CUSTOMERS

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ABSTRACT

For a long time there were efforts for FDI in the retail sector so that the trader can reap the benefit of FDI. Retail trade contributes around 10-11% of India's GDP and currently employs over 4 crores of people. Recently, a great debate has cropped up against the government plans for FDI in the Indian retail sector. The main fear of FDI in retail trade is that it will certainly disrupt the livelihood of the poor people engaged in this trade. The opening of big markets or international outlets will not necessarily absorb them; rather they may try to establish the monopoly power in the country. However, so many positive factors are also there in favour of FDI in Indian retail service. Some of the large international retailers like Wal-Mart, Metro and Carrefour already operate their own large outlets in India but they are limited by to sell only to store owners or institutional buyers as a wholesaler since the government allows 100 per cent foreign ownership of firms engaged only in wholesale cash and carry retail.

The present paper highlights the views of consumers and retailers in Moradabad region and tries to analyse the impact of FDI in retail sector on customers.

Key words: FDI, Retail, Moradabad, Indian Customers

INTRODUCTION

In 2004, The High Court of Delhi defined the term 'retail' as a sale for final consumption in contrast to a sale for further sale or processing (i.e. wholesale); *A sale to the ultimate consumer.*

Retailing can be said to be the interface between the producer and the individual consumer buying for personal consumption. This excludes direct interface between the manufacturer and institutional buyers such as the government and other bulk customers. Retailing is the last link that connects the individual consumer with the manufacturing and distribution chain. A retailer is involved in the act of selling goods to the individual consumer at a margin of profit.

Division of Retail Industry

The retail industry is mainly divided into:-

- 1) Organised and
- 2) Unorganised Retailing

Organized retailing is based on the principle of unity and unorganized retailing is based on the principle of singularity. Both organized and unorganized retailing is found in most countries throughout the world. India and China are strong examples of countries in which unorganized retailing dominated their markets. Today these countries have a growing economy because of the influx of organized retailers into their markets.

The Indian retail sector is highly fragmented with 95 per cent of its business being run by the unorganized retailers. The organized retail however is at a very nascent stage. The sector is the largest source of employment after agriculture, and has deep penetration into rural India generating more than 10 per cent of India's GDP.

Those opposing FDI in the retail sector argue that a large number of small and medium retail traders will lose their livelihood. But they forget one important thing — that there is no quality control over the goods we get from them. The consumers are at their mercy. Milk, edible oils, pulses and cereals are all adulterated. When retail giants of international repute enter the market, unscrupulous traders will either lose their business or have to assure quality. Today, the end consumer, and not the shopper, is the centre of the Indian FMCG company's universe. That's not the scenario in other developed markets. The difference is crucial. In modern retail, when a consumer walks into a hypermarket and buys a pack of detergent, s/he makes a choice between 10 and 15 brands and then chooses one out of 400 packs. That's the starting point of the art and science of shoppers' choice in the modern retail world. Everything, from packaging to promotion to pricing, is designed to get the attention of the shopper. The share of organized retail to total retail trade in India is hardly 5 % against 66 % in Japan, 30 % in Indonesia and 20 % in China

It is high time for India to allow FDI in all possible categories to bring more competition in the market and reduce the gap between farm prices and retail prices.

Organized retail acts as a cushion against inflation

Unlike kiranas, some of the organized retailers cut through various levels of middlemen to source directly from farmers. Since they have multiple outlets, these corporate backed chains are also able to pass on savings to the consumers by purchasing large volumes.

Kiranas deal with consumer goods brands in low volumes. Since these firms do not share good margins, kiranas make it up by charging the MRP without discount. But unlike kiranas, organized retailers have to make it worth the consumer's while to drive out, brave not only traffic but parking hassles and shopping queues. This is where their unique selling point of everyday low prices come in. To draw consumers, retailers squeeze suppliers and ensure efficiency in categories which drive footfalls. They balance it out by enjoying higher margins in categories where impulse buying is high. Organized chains retail at lower prices even at a time when food inflation hovers at nine percent.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The present paper aims at the following objectives:

- To determine the impact of FDI in Retail sector on customers
- To analyze the attraction of Indian market for international players

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of various retailers and consumers has been taken about the pros, cons and impact of FDI in Retail sector. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on FDI in Retail.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to implementation of FDI in Retail. The discussions were based on key initiatives with emphasis on impact on customers. The researchers also use the secondary data published in various Business dailies.

FDI IN RETAIL

The Union Cabinet has approved 51% FDI in multi-brand retail and raised the cap on FDI in single-brand retail from 51% to 100%. It means that global retailers such as Walmart, Carrefour, Tesco and others can set up mega deep-discount stores in the country through joint ventures with Indian firms, where the foreign partner can hold up 51% equity

Single brand retail companies such as Swedish furnishing giant Ikea or sporting goods and equipment major Reebok can set up stores of their own in India through their own subsidiaries. Till now they were required to set up stores through joint ventures in India that allowed the foreign partner to own up to 51% equity.

The Indian Government has come with a string of conditions. At least half of the FDI should be made in back-end infrastructure such as cold-chain and warehousing, the minimum FDI in

any multi-brand retail project should be \$100 million (around Rs 500 crore), state governments can prohibit FDI in retail in their states if they wish to, stores can be set up only in cities with a population of at least 1 million, and at least 30% of the value of manufactured items procured should be sourced from Indian small and medium enterprises.

Important events about FDI in multi brand retail

January 1997	During NDA Government, Approval for 100 percent FDI in wholesale business through automatic route
October 2003	Metro Company of Germany was the first cash and carry international chain in India.
January 2006	During UPA Government, Approval for 51 percent FDI in single brand retail.
November 2006	Agreement between Walmart of America and Bharti Enterprises for retail business.
February 2007	UPA Government gave assignment to ICREAR to do research on the impact of organized retail on small kirana shops
August 2007	ICREAR in its report wants to give vast base to retail
May 2008	The report of ICREAR states that the impact of organized retail on small kirana shops will have a limited impact.
August 2008	Agreement between Tesco, Britain and Trent of Tata Group
December 2010	Carrefour opened its first single brand store in India.
November 2011	The Union Cabinet has approved 51% FDI in multi-brand retail and raised the cap on FDI in single-brand retail from 51% to 100%.

Following are some facts on India's retail sector:

1. The retail sector in the nation of 1.2 billion people is estimated to have annual sales of \$500 billion, with nearly 90 percent of the market controlled by tiny family-run shops.
2. About 8 percent of India's population employed in retail.
3. Organised retail, or large chains, makes up less than 10 percent of the market, but is expanding at 20 percent a year. This is driven by the emergence of shopping centres and malls, and a middle class of close to 300 million people that is growing at nearly 2 percent a year.
4. India also allows FDI in cash-and-carry, or wholesale, ventures. Restrictions on foreign investment in retail existed because of opposition from millions of small shopkeepers who are valuable vote banks during elections.
5. Previously, India allowed 51 percent FDI in single-brand retail and 100 percent in wholesale operations, but no ownership in multi-brand retail.

LOCAL COMPANIES

1. Pantaloon Retail, India's largest listed retailer and part of the Future Group, runs stores under its lifestyle brands Pantaloon and Central. Future also operates the Big Bazaar hypermarket chain and supermarket brand Food Bazaar, under the unlisted

Future Value Retail. The group has 500 stores across formats, and occupies a total retail space of 15 million square feet in India. Future has for long been linked to France's Carrefour for a partnership in hypermarkets. Pantaloon's net profit increased 69 percent to 1.42 billion rupees (\$27.33 million) in the year to end-June, on net sales of 122.1 billion rupees.

2. Second-ranked Reliance Retail is part of Reliance Industries, India's largest listed group headed by Mukesh Ambani, who tops the Forbes India rich list. Reliance Retail operates 1,050 stores across neighbourhood stores, supermarkets and hypermarkets. In the year to end-March, it posted a net loss of 4.46 billion rupees on sales of \$1.1 billion, a tiny share of the group's total revenue of \$53 billion. It has said it doesn't plan to partner with any global retailer.
3. Shoppers Stop, part of the K Raheja Group which operates in real estate, has around 644 stores across brands and formats and 12 Hypercity hypermarkets. It operates 3.93 million square feet of retail space and its loss-making Hypercity is open to partnerships with foreign groups. It posted a net loss of 15.1 million rupees on sales of 5.81 billion rupees in the year to end-March.
4. Trent, part of Tata Group, operates 72 stores across formats and runs the Westside range of apparel stores, and hypermarkets under Star Bazaar. It signed a franchisee agreement with Tesco Plc under which Star Bazaar shops use the British firm's supply chains and infrastructure. Trent made a net profit of 74.9 million rupees on net sales of 15.2 billion rupees during fiscal 2011.
5. Aditya Birla Retail is the unlisted retail arm of India's telecoms-to-cement conglomerate Aditya Birla Group headed by Kumar Mangalam Birla, who ranks 97th on the Forbes global rich list. The company operates around 580 supermarket and hypermarket stores under the More brand. The loss-making retail unit expects to be profitable after tax by 2015. It has said it will evaluate partnerships with global firms.

MAJOR FOREIGN COMPANIES

1. Wal-Mart Stores Inc has a cash-and-carry operation with Indian partner Bharti Enterprises, the parent of leading mobile provider Bharti Airtel, and will add up to 10 new cash-and-carry stores this year to its 6 existing stores.
2. Tesco, Britain's largest retailer has a tie-up with Trent's Star Bazaar hypermarket chain. Tesco is also looking to enter the wholesale market through the tie-up.
3. Germany's Metro AG operates 6 wholesale stores in India and will add up to 4 new stores this year.

4. Carrefour has 2 cash-and-carry stores in India's capital, New Delhi. The world's No. 2 retailer has been seeking a local partner to enter the hyper or supermarket sectors.

GENERAL PROS AND CONS OF FDI IN RETAIL

	Pros	Cons
Employment Opportunities	Definitely jobs will be created for processing, sorting, logistics and marketing	Experience from International scenario shows that super markets invariably displace small retailers. Jobs in the manufacturing sector will be lost because it might be possible that international retail makes purchases internationally. There will be a redistribution of jobs with some drying up and some new ones sprouting.
Farmers	It will help farmers secure remunerative prices by eliminating exploitative middlemen.	This still remain questionable.
Supply Chains	It can ensure supply chain efficiencies. This could bring down food inflation as perishables will not be wasted in huge quantities.	The argument that only foreign players can create the supply chain for farm produce is not genuine.

INDIAN RETAIL MARKET IMPORTANT FOR INTERNATIONAL PLAYERS

Why Indian retail market is important for the international players? The reasons are obvious:

- India ranked 5th in the Global A.T Kearney Retail Development Index,
- Second only to China in Asia, least saturated of all global markets studied, the least competitive of all global markets studied, implies lower barriers of entry for global players, considering tremendous market size, excellent potential for foreign players.
- Apart from that, the economic position of Indian middle class favours the entry of retail giants. According to Euromonitor Retail Survey Indian consumer sector is undergoing higher growth rate it states that increase in disposable income of middle class households is the basic cause of attraction.

IMPACT OF FDI IN RETAILING ON THE CUSTOMERS

New FDI policy will surely bring forth benefits to Customers, Economy and Infrastructure in the country. We must not forget that consumers are the most important part of our economy today. They will also be the biggest gainers from FDI in retail, thereby benefiting the entire country. In a pan-Indian survey conducted over the weekend of 3 December 2011, overwhelming majority of consumers and farmers in and around ten major cities across the country support the retail reforms. Over 90 per cent of consumers said FDI in retail will bring

down prices and offer a wider choice of goods. Nearly 78 per cent of farmers said they will get better prices for their produce from multi-format stores. Over 75 per cent of the traders claimed their marketing resources will continue to be needed to push sales through multiple channels, but they may have to accept lower margins for greater volumes.

1. The government allowed 51% FDI in multi-brand retail, but restricted it to cities with population in excess of one million. It also raised FDI in single brand to 100%. As per the 2011 census, consumers in the 53 most populated cities of the country add up to over 122 million. In contrast, the numbers of people connected with retailing in the country is about 40 million, according to several estimates.
2. Buyers are expected to benefit the most from the increased competition in the retail industry in terms of prices and quality. Competition will push prices down and improve quality of products.
3. Customers will get large collection of great quality of goods and merchandise at reasonable prices.
4. A crucial argument against foreign investment in retail is the belief that small retailers will suffer. This, in some sense, suggests that low price is all that counts in the retailing industry. Small retailers' offer of personalized service, home delivery and credit seems to have been given little importance. One question is whether customers, used to these services for long, will give them up easily.
5. Large retail has typically succeeded where consumers have been willing to buy in large quantities to avail volume-related discounts. In a country where the marketing ethos has been dominated by the paisa pack, and marketers obsess about the fact that the unit outlay for a commodity must be small for it to be attractive, another question is whether there is a willingness to make large outlays. There is also the so-called "car" problem in retail: Only if large parts of the population own cars would they be able to carry 24 cartons of orange juice and 2kg tubs of ice cream conveniently. If only car owners are targeted by big retail, one wonders if there would be a material impact on the small store.
6. Malls have now become rather a destination for the middle class in not only all the big metros but also Tier II & III cities. No format or player will get a cakewalk in Indian market triggered with Multi-brand retail outlets selling unbranded fresh agriculture produce, including fruits, vegetables, flowers, grains, pulses, fresh poultry, fishery and meat products. Indian consumer is more likely to continue to patronizing the regular local vendors as these small stores offer superlative services like Home

Delivery, Monthly Credit Account etc. The large format players will focus more on satisfying customers' monthly needs of products and services.

7. Indian consumers are the savviest with clear focus on value and quality. Indians love to buy and cook fresh and they will continue to visit their regular local market vendors and vegetable vendors to take care of their daily needs
8. Permitting foreign investment in food-based retailing is likely to ensure adequate flow of capital into the country and its productive use, in a manner likely to promote the welfare of all sections of society, particularly farmers and consumers.
9. Organised retail provides higher quality of goods on account of the pre-defined and stringent standards adopted by the retailers. And of course the price will be cheaper. Studies have shown that consumers, on an average, will save at least 10% on daily use goods.
10. Today consumers have a choice of shopping at malls prepared across their towns and cities or in the kirana stores in their neighbourhoods. Tomorrow the choice gets bigger. Giant megastores will sell labeled items like stationery, footwear, clothes etc at deep discounts.
11. Given the condition that foreign retailers can only open outlets in cities with a population of one million or more, more than 75 percent of India's eight million consumer-goods stocking kiranas will be protected from the foreign invasion, since they are located in rural India.
12. Consumers have the right to choose if they want to visit Wal-Mart or the local kirana store. Chances are, they'll patronise both. The point is, they, not politicians and producers, should decide who they want to buy their groceries from.
13. Today, apart from the foreign multi-brand retailer, we have every kind of foreign retailer in the country. Consumers can choose to have a Pepsi or a Thums Up, a coffee from Barista or Cafe Coffee Day or ice cream from Amul or Baskin Robbins. No foreign company has managed to come into India and wipe out the entire competition.
14. In retail stores, we find products from Nestle and Hindustan Unilever sitting besides those from Godrej Consumer Products and Dabur. Competition forces companies to evolve and adapt to consumer tastes. Those that learn to do that survive, whether they are local or foreign. If Indians find they don't like shopping at Wal-Mart, they won't. And if we're afraid that suppliers might be squeezed by giant foreign retailers, we need to create rules to prevent that from happening, not stop foreigners entering the market altogether.

OTHER ADVANTAGES OF FDI IN RETAIL

There are many advantages of FDI in retail in India. Some of the positives of opening of Multi brand retail like Walmart in India as a whole are as follows:

1. FDI can be a powerful catalyst to spur competition in the retail industry, due to the current scenario of low competition and poor productivity
2. Farmers will benefit from opening of Multi brand retails like Walmart in India as they will be earning 30-40% more because they can sell their products directly to these retail chains, cutting the profit made by middle men in between.
3. General Middle class customers will also benefit due to removal of this middle men in buying and selling of products.
4. Customers will have more option available in buying whatever he wants to buy as more brands will be available at his/her disposal.
5. Employment opportunities will be generated in form of sales man, counter boys etc.
6. Employment will move from unorganized sector to organized sector.

INDIAN RETAIL REFORMS ON HOLD

India's government had put the FDI retail reforms on hold until it reaches consensus within the ruling coalition. The resistance to Indian retail reforms is primarily because it has been badly sold. Mamata Banerjee, the chief minister of West Bengal and the leader of the Trinamool Congress, announced her opposition to retail reform. Other states whose Chief Ministers have either personally announced opposition or announced reluctance to implement the retail reforms are Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Madhya Pradesh. Chief Ministers of many states have not made a personal statement in opposition or support of India needing retail reforms. Gujarat, Kerala, Karnataka and Rajasthan are examples of these states.

CONCLUSION

Two decades ago, we heard the same cries against liberalization of the Indian economy. Well, 20 years on, most of Indian industry has survived and even thrived. In fact, our IT industry, one of the most exposed to global competition, ranks among the best in the world. The policy of allowing 100% FDI in single brand retail can benefit both the foreign retailer and the Indian partner – foreign players get local market knowledge, while Indian companies can access global best management practices, designs and technological know-how. By partially opening this sector, the government was able to reduce the pressure from its trading partners in bilateral/ multilateral negotiations and could demonstrate India's intentions in liberalizing this sector in a phased manner.

If organized retail is to grow at its own projected pace, the Union Government needs to accord it an industry status first. It needs to also implement the goods and service tax, simplify taxes and invest on infrastructure development.

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